

Quick Start Guide:

Protocol for quantifying and modeling light scattering in coral microskeletons

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Overview

This guide provides a quick walkthrough for running the OCT optical property analysis pipeline and Monte Carlo simulations using the example dataset provided in the Zenodo repository.

The full methodological details are described in the associated STAR Protocols manuscript. This guide is intended as a visual companion to help users quickly set up the software environment, run the analysis, and verify that the pipeline works correctly on their system.

The example dataset acts as a test dataset, allowing users to validate the workflow before applying the protocol to their own OCT data.

1. Download the dataset

Download the [Zenodo archive](#) by clicking “Download all” under Files.

Extract the .zip file to a local directory.

Create the following folders:

- “OCT calibration” - move and extract Calibration TIFF files.zip.
- “OCT_Fungia” - move all .tiff files starting with “fungia”.

2. Install Required Software

This pipeline requires:

- [MATLAB \(tested with MATLAB R2024 or newer\)](#). Download for your platform (Windows/Mac/Linux). System requirements are mentioned in this page.
- MATLAB toolboxes: ‘Image Processing ToolboxImage’, ‘Processing Toolbox and Computer Vision’, and ‘volumeViewer’

In MATLAB, go to Home → Environment → ‘Get Add-Ons’.

This will open the Add-On Explorer. Then search and install each toolbox.

3. Run calibration program

Open the MATLAB file 'STARprotocols_OCT_calibration.m' and make sure you are in the 'Editor' tab. Click on 'Run all sections'.

When prompted, select the calibration directory (i.e., “OCT calibration” folder) and click ‘Open’.

The following figures will be generated:

B-scan images:

A-scan profiles:

and finally, the calibration of the OCT system:

The calibration plot shows expected reflectance (R; in log10) on the x-axis and measured OCT signal on the y-axis. The fitted line represents the system calibration used to convert OCT signal into reflectance.

The code saves the final figure and all calibration coefficients a and b and OCT systems constants.

4. Select regions of interest (ROI) from OCT images

Open the MATLAB file 'OCT_coral_area.m'. Click on the 'Run all sections' button. Select the calibration constants file (.mat) from the folder "OCT calibration" and click 'Open'. Then, enter the number of slopes to fit (use "1" for this example) and click OK.

Select the data directory (i.e., the folder "OCT_Fungia"), click Open. Then, select the .tiff file 'fungia_primary1.tiff'.

Select a region of interest (ROI) within the OCT image by clicking the start and end points along the x-axis. For this example, you may select a single point (e.g., pixel X = 469) to reproduce the results shown here.

For each pixel in that range, the calibrated OCT profile signal (Reflectance vs. depth) is generated and saved.

A vertical white line is added to the OCT image showing the selected area.

The program will ask if you want to select another area in the image. Click “No” (you can click of course yes once you work on your own data or if you want to explore more regions in the skeleton shown on the OCT b-scan).

The program will ask if you wish to select another file. Click “No”.

Once done, the program will save the data to your folder as .csv file (i.e., “OCT_data.csv”).

5. Extract optical properties

Run the optical property extraction script ‘generate_murhograd.m’.

You will be prompted to select the folder directory containing the .csv file (e.g., “OCT_Fungia” folder), then the file “OCT_data.csv”.

This script generates a lookup grid that links OCT signal parameters (attenuation coefficient - μ and backscatter coefficient - ρ) to optical properties (scattering coefficient - μ_s and scattering anisotropy - g), and then uses it to estimate these properties from experimental data:

This script produces:

- A visual optical grid plot showing the relationship between μ and ρ and the underlying optical properties (μ_s and g).
- A .csv file with predicted optical properties (μ_s and g) for each experimental data point (in this example, only one point from our extracted OCT image).
- A summary CSV file with median optical properties per group (e.g., per area). The grouping factor can be modified by the user in line 39 (individual data points) and line 40 (summary data points).

In this example:

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	folder_name	GroupCount	median_Mu1	median_Rho1	pg	pmus
2	OCT_Fungia	1	1.451173981	1.48E-07	0.979141423	4.3522115

6. Run Monte Carlo light propagation simulations

The extracted optical properties can be used in the Monte Carlo simulation code to model light propagation within 3D coral skeleton structures.

Open 'MC3D.m' and click "Run all sections".

Set up geometry parameters:

Configure number of coral layers. Select "No" (i.e., using a single coral layer):

Confirm the STL file is in mm (select “Yes (mm)”):

Assign water optical properties:

Assign coral layer optical properties (look at the predicted data from “OCT_data_example_summary_predictions.csv” saved in “OCT_Fungia” folder):

Set simulation time and virtual beam radius:

You will be asked if to prompt to start the simulation. Click "Yes".
Then you will load the 3D coral model "fungia_fungites.stl" found in your main folder with all the MATLAB codes.

Once simulation is complete, the program will save the following:

Histogram showing the distribution of fluence rate across all surface voxels (saved as 'fungia_fungites_histogram.png'):

A 3D heat map showing how light intensity (fluence) is distributed across the coral surface (saved as 'fungia_fungites_3D_fluence.png'):

A bird's-eye view of the light intensity (fluence), useful for seeing "hot spots" of light concentration (saved as 'funiga_fungites_2D_topview.png'):

Once the pipeline runs successfully using the example dataset, users can apply the same workflow to their own OCT data.